

FAMILY EDUCATION STRATEGIES AND PERSONAL FEATURES OF MOTHERS IN CHILDREN WITH EARLY SIGNS OF BEHAVIORAL DISORDERS

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Abstract

Purpose. The article discusses the issues of maternal attitudes towards young children, which determine the formation of mental personality structures, and serve as a parameter for the formation of a healthy personality. An overview of approaches to the role of parental attitude in the formation of mental, physical and emotional health of a child is presented. Maternal attitude is considered as the basic mechanism of personality victimization in case of violation of maternal attachment. Attachment is considered as the primary setting, transferred by the child in the future to all social relationships, and determining the level of his cognitive, psychoemotional and psychomotor development. The role of mental deprivation in the formation of the child's primary victim vulnerability is outlined.

Methodology. The methodology is based on the assumption that maternal parenting styles depend on her personal characteristics, social factors, and psychological reasons for the birth of a child. The mother's actual parenting attitude will affect the disruption in the upbringing of children. An analysis of a study of 128 women with children under four years old is presented.

Results. Factor analysis made it possible to identify four main types of maternal attitudes towards children responsible for the specifics of the emergence of victimhood. The factorial determinants of the emergence and manifestation of different types of parental relationship have been determined.

Conclusions. There are consistent differences in children's behavior disorders with different styles of maternal relationships.

Keywords: maternal attachment, maternal attitude, victimization, young children, behavioral disorders

Introduction

The significance of the parent-child relationship for the mental development of young children is a well-established fact. In recent times, there has been a large number of studies dedicated to this topic (Frosch, Schoppe-Sullivan, & O'Banion, 2019; Reiss, Ganiban, Leve, et al. 2023; Andronnikova, 2023). However, questions about the specificity of the mother-child relationship, the mechanisms of its formation, and its influence on the child's development still remain relevant.

The development of social relations, geopolitical processes, the impact of urbanization, female emancipation, and scientific and technological progress have led to a certain narrowing of the role of family pedagogy in child rearing. Parent-child relationships have largely come to be determined by the social environment.

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The shift in gender and ethnic values, including in terms of the mother's role in child upbringing and her attitude towards the family in general, is an important trend of modernity. As a result of the observed geopolitical, world-systemic, socio-economic processes, the priority of the role of the "mother" has shifted in favor of the role of the "successful woman". The value system of the modern woman has changed. The values of

being a homemaker and family caretaker have been replaced by the values of a successful career, education, and material well-being. Gender expectations and the content of corresponding female roles have changed. However, it is precisely maternal care, love, and attention that remain the foundation for shaping a child's personality, their psychological well-being, and psychological "health".

Reiss, Ganiban, Leve et al. (2023) note that it is the system of interactions between mother and child that plays the most influential role in their emotional, cognitive, and neurobiological well-being. This position is supported by other authors who study early childhood issues. Such keen interest is far from accidental, as it is found that the first years of life are a period of the most intensive personality development, laying the foundation for physical, mental, and moral health. The future of the child largely depends on the conditions in which these years unfold.

Researches made by many authors (Freud, 1999; Erickson, 1993; Horney, 2016; Winnicott, 2005; Bratman, Radionova 1999 etc.) speak of the criticality of the quality of care of the mother in the first weeks and months of life.

Georgiou (2008) in his research of 377 children and their mothers, notes that there is a line of influence between mother's responsiveness, overprotection, and the experience of child victimization in school. Miguel, Villodas, Bagner & Thompson (2018) in their research identified parenting patterns of mothers as a potential pathway through which symptoms of maternal depression affect a child's behavioral problems. This is in line with research by Gravener, Rogosch, Oshri et al (2012),

which found associations between behavioral problems in toddlers (average age of 20 months), childhood attachment and maternal depression. Also finds confirmation in researches of other authors (Śliwerski, Kossakowska, Jarecka, Świtalska, & Bielawska-Batorowicz, 2020; Pagani, Harandian, Necsa, & Harbec, 2023).

The general conclusion of many approaches that research the role of the mother in the child's life is the statement of the child's need for the presence and maintenance of a sense of security and confidence in its provision on the part of adults, primarily the mother. (Śliwerski, Kossakowska, Jarecka, Świtalska, & Bielawska-Batorowicz, 2020; Scheid, Miller-Graff, & Guzmán, 2020). It is ensured by the manifestation of an adult's care and demonstration to the child of his positive and emotional attitude towards him. Pagani, Harandian, Necsa, & Harbec (2023) pay special attention to how postpartum depression in mothers affects child development.

The focus of the research conducted by Russian scientists is primarily on the function of the mother in providing emotional comfort to the child, viewed through the lens of distorted mother-child interactions. According to several authors (Varga, 1986; Filippova, 2001; Andronnikova, O.O., 2023), it is precisely the deformation of parent-child relationships that becomes the source of disruption in the child's emotional and personal sphere and mental health from infancy to adolescence. This includes studies on parental attitudes, parenting styles, and various aspects of parent-child interactions.

Considering the causes and mechanisms of such influence as a central theme, the authors (Varga 1986; Koloskova 1989; Skoblo, Dubovik 1992, etc.) point out the basic attitude towards the world which is formed in early childhood (Varga [4], Koloskova[7], Skoblo[8], etc.). Sufficient attention is paid to the construct of the "inner world of a person" (Vasilyuk, 2001) or the "psychological space of personality" (Nartova-Bochaver, 2002), which include basic self-conceptions and conceptions of the world. The content of this construct is characterized by an actively trusting attitude towards the world (Koloskova, 1989) and a stable positive-emotional mood. The formation of the content of basic trust in the world relies on the subjective experience of the child, which is directly dependent on the mother's behavior. In addition to meeting the child's physiological and emotional needs, the mother's role also includes providing support for the child's active attitude towards the world. In this case, the mother perceives the child not as an object, but as a subject of emotional experiences and activities.

Filippova (2002), studying the emotional well-being of a child at different ages and its correlation with the mother's attitude and behavior, notes that it is not only manifested in a predominantly positive mood. The consequence of a mother's positive attitude toward a child is the development of a constructive style of experiencing the results of activities, successes and failures, the development of cognitive motivation and the child's activity, the ability to engage in joint activities

with adults, the attitude toward adult evaluation, the development of self-control, the style of experiencing the situation of separation from a close adult, and the experience of the family situation.

The maternal attitude is singled out as a basic parameter influencing the course of early ontogenesis, and we consider it as a determinant of the emergence of victimization in a particular environment. The characteristics of the parents (primarily the mother), as the primary "agent" of socialization, are the social component of victimization in the four-dimensional approach biological-psychological-social in cultural determination. The process of socialization of the child through the violation of maternal attachment becomes the fundamental parameter of victimogenesis. This position is supported by research by Alizadeh Maralani, Mirnasab, & Hashemi (2019), who studied in a sample of 300 elementary school students what parenting style is associated with victimization. The authors noted that the authoritarian parenting style is associated with aggressive student behavior, while the victim's children were often brought up in families with a tolerant parenting style.

Considering the phenomenon of maternal attachment, it is necessary to note its unconscious nature and structural structure, containing affective, cognitive and behavioral components (Vasilenko, 2011), the content of which is determined by the experience gained in interaction with the mother in early childhood. Vasilenko (2011) designates attachment as a primary social attitude, which is subsequently transferred by the child to all social relations. Attachment disorder leads, according to many authors (Bowlby, 2003; Bozhovich, 2001; Winnicott, 2005 and others), to the emergence of maternal deprivation and personality development disorders. The influence of maternal attachment on adolescent behavior is presented in researches Silinskas, Kiuru, Aunola, Metsäpelto, Lerkkanen, & Nurmi, (2020). The authors note that it is maternal attachment that creates the context that amplifies the influence of parental stress on adolescent behavior.

Thus, the specificity of interaction between mother and child at an early age is the basis for the emergence of victim processes. Lack of maternal attachment, its low quality, will affect the psycho-emotional, psychomotor and cognitive development of the child, determine the specifics of his self-attitude and the level of self-esteem. Violation of any of the attachment components will lead to the corresponding type of victimization and the emergence of victim behavior.

Violations of the basic mechanism of maternal attachment, according to many authors, lead to mental deprivation. So Yaroslavtseva (2014) considers the phenomenon of mental deprivation as a psychological state, manifested in immaturity and distortions of personal development and psychophysiological activity of the body, provoking social and psychological maladjustment. Considering the role of mental deprivation in the formation of different types of victimization, it is necessary to take into account the primary conditions associated with the peculiarities of the perinatal period and the presence of biological pathology. Let us designate the specificity of the impact of maternal attach-

ment on the further trajectory of the child's development, depending on the primary type: normative ontogenesis, dysontogenesis of psychological initiation, dysontogenesis of biological initiation, dysontogenesis (Andronnikova, 2019).

The initially adaptive type of development in a situation of violation of maternal attachment and the mother's demonstration of emotional coldness and rejection, depending on the level of resilience, can further maintain the trajectory of adequate social and psychological development, subject to compensation from a significant microenvironment. In the absence of devictimizing compensation, the violation of maternal attachment leads to the emergence of victimogenesis of socio-psychological initiation. The consequence of the absence of maternal attachment will be the difficulty of building emotionally close relationships, violation of personality boundaries, a pronounced tendency to the formation of dependence. The violation of maternal attachment and the chosen styles of maternal attitude will have a huge impact on the child with primary maladjustment of the biological type. In conditions of primary biological vulnerability, low maternal attachment and inappropriate styles of maternal attitudes lead to a victimizing trajectory of development, with corresponding emotional, behavioral cognitive attitudes (Andronnikova, 2023).

The decisive role in building the trajectory of individual development is played by maternal attachment and attitude to the child in the case of dysontogenesis of biological or psychological initiation. It is the maternal attitude that will determine the opportunities for devictimization and the formation of a non-victimized development strategy. However, if, in a situation of dysontogenetic development, the formation of the basic emotional mood with the corresponding cognitive parameters arising as a result of the maternal attitude is disturbed, then ontogenesis shifts to the zone of victimogenesis, with the corresponding types of socio-psychological disorders.

Thus, it is maternal attachment and the general attitude of the mother to the child, which is manifested in the strategies of maternal education in early childhood, that is the fundamental parameter of ontogenesis. An empirical research was carried out to investigate various aspects of maternal attitudes and the factors of their determination.

The hypotheses of the study are as follows:

1. The style of maternal relationship with the child is determined by the psychological and socio-economic characteristics of women, as well as by the peculiarities of their upbringing in the parental family.

2. Reliable differences in the signs of behavioral disorders in children will be observed with different styles of maternal relationship.

Materials and methods

The research was conducted on a random sample of young women (128 people), aged 20 to 30, the condition was the presence of children under the age of 4 years. Children were monitored by specialists for the presence of behavioral disorders, including those of a victim nature. All participants in the study were informed about its goals and gave voluntary consent to the participate. Women have different social status (housewives, employees, workers), varying levels of material well-being (from low to high) and marital statuses (married and single mothers). We did not classify women into subgroups based on the type of child behavioral disorder.

We used such empirical methods as questioning, testing. The test material is presented in the form of techniques such as: 16 factor personality questionnaire 16PF by R. Cattell (form C); questionnaire "Measurement of parental attitudes and reactions" (PARI), authors E. Schaefer and K. Bell; the method of diagnosing parental attitudes (ORO), authors A.Ya. Varga and V.V. Stolin. The multifactorial personality questionnaire PF-16 author R. Cattell (form C) is aimed at diagnosing a person's personality traits and shows the balance between two opposing personality characteristics. The Parental Attitudes and Reactions Inventory (PARI) is designed to examine the mother's attitudes toward various aspects of family life and the family roles she represents. Reveals 23 aspects, 15 of which relate to parent-child relationships (emotional contact, emotional distance, concentration on the child), 8 describe the attitude to the family role. The method of diagnosing parental attitudes (PDA) is aimed at identifying parental attitudes towards children (3-10 years old). The questionnaire contains 61 questions and allows you to identify the type of relationship as a system of feelings towards the child.

After conducting the initial testing, a comprehensive examination was conducted to analyze the social and psychological characteristics of the women who took part in the study. Following this, a factor analysis of the gathered data was performed in order to identify specific factors associated with their upbringing. In prospect using the Kruskal - Wallis test, the difference in the presence of violations in the behavior of the children of mothers, divided into subgroups according to the method of diagnosing parental attitudes, was revealed.

Results

The questionnaires were processed and the socio-economic characteristics of the women participating in the study were highlighted. The data is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Socio-economic characteristics of women participating in the study	
Question items in the questionnaire	B %
Family status	
Married	57,14
Single	16,3
Civil marriage	8,16
Remarriage	8,16
Single-parent family in divorce	10,2
Education	
Higher	63,3
Secondary - special	22,44
General only	16,33
Availability of work	
Works	73,5
Does not work	26,5
Material wealth	
Average	57,14
Above average	20,4
High	8,16
Short	6,12
Dependence on parents	16,3
Availability of housing	
Availability of separate housing	41,22
Live with parents	38,68
Renting housing	20,1
Relationships with parents	
Good	73,5
Conflict	24,5
Having brothers and sisters	
Have brothers or sisters	67,34
No brothers or sisters	30,6
Relationships with brothers/sisters	
Good relationship with them	57,14
Neutral	22,66
Conflict	20,2

According to the table, the following "risk factors" can be identified in relation to negative attitudes towards the family role and the child: divorce (10.2%); lack of professional education (16.33%); dependency on parents (16.3%); conflicting relationships with parents (24.5%); conflicting relationships with siblings (20.2%).

Table 2 presents the psychological characteristics of the women participating in the study. The questionnaire included questions aimed at identifying planned pregnancy, reasons for its preservation, and the position of the child in the mother's value system. The questionnaire also included a question aimed at self-assessment of the type of relationship with the subject, when she was a child in her parental family from her mother's perspective.

Table 2

Psychological characteristics of women participating in the study	
Question items in the questionnaire	Sample in %
Attitude towards motherhood	
The gender of the child is the same as expected	
Yes	77,5
No	22,44
Was the pregnancy planned?	
Planned	30,6
Unexpected	32,65
Something in between	36,7
Motives for maintaining pregnancy	
child from a loved one	59,2
for the sake of the child	57,14
maintaining relationships	30,6
meeting social expectations	8,16
maintaining one's own health	48,9
receiving material reward	2,04
acquiring mother status	34,7
as a protest	10,2
abandonment of the past	14,3
Parenting style of the subjects' parents (by self-assessment)	
Authoritarian	30,6
Democratic	40,8
Conniving	28,6
Guardian	8,2
The child's place in the value system	
First	55,1
Second	22,44
Below	22,44

According to the results of the Parental Relationship Assessment (ORO) methodology, prevailing parenting strategies were identified (Table 3). The categorization into a specific parenting type was based on the expression of scale indicators in the methodology: according to the leading scale. The transition from the

ORO methodology scales to the adopted classification was necessary to align the parenting style that the participants identified as their parents' strategy towards them with the one they themselves implement towards their child.

Table 3

Predominant maternal strategies		
Parenting style/ maternal attitude	Methodology scales, parental attitude questionnaire, OPO	Entire sample in %
Democratic	Cooperation	25,1
Authoritarian *	Control	25,0
Permissive *	Control	39,8
Guardian	Symbiosis	10,1

* this style was determined based on the Cooperation scale and the degree of expression of the leading behavioral type.

Further, based on the obtained diagnostic results, a factor analysis was conducted. The four factors obtained, corresponding to the types of maternal relationship, allowed for the identification of the specificity of personal characteristics, socio-demographic, and psychological factors that determine the type of relationship with the child. Comparing the behavioral characteristics of children with mothers of the identified types of relationship helped achieve the set objectives and test hypotheses.

The discussion

The factor analysis of various parameters of the parental attitude of women made it possible to single out four main factors with the corresponding type of

upbringing, which reveal the specifics of the determination of the emergence of the type of parental attitude and the peculiarities of its manifestation.

Firstly, it is a set of parameters associated with authoritarianism in the relationship between parents and children (25% of the entire sample). Considering the factorial weight of various parameters, the following aspects can be distinguished as significant:

The authoritarian type of parenting attitude will be characterized by such parameters as a high level of emotional distance with the child (0.844), lack of optimal emotional contact (-0.576), and a low level of concentration on the child's needs (-0.588). Much attention in such a family is paid to the organization of life and household needs (0.65), the emotional and other needs

of the child are often ignored (0.796). Significant characteristics of the parental sphere of such mothers are the underdevelopment of parental feelings (0.757), the projection of their own undesirable qualities onto the child (0.764) and the introduction of conflict between spouses into the sphere of upbringing (0.63). This means that there is an emotional rejection of the child in the family (0.836), based on the projection of his own undesirable qualities onto the child, increased moral normativity and excessive demands (0.64), implemented through a system of severe sanctions (0.639), up to cruel treatment (0.725). Poor development of parental feelings correlates with a high level of rejection of the parent himself in childhood (0.56). The parameter of introducing conflicts between spouses into the sphere of upbringing will be manifested in the form of a difference in parental messages caused by competition with each other and the need to express dissatisfaction through seemingly acceptable ways of "caring for the child". In addition, this parameter is associated with the instability of the upbringing style (0.719), manifested in the inconsistency of sanctions for the child's behavioral manifestations, his infantilization and a decrease in initiative (0.717). Characteristic features of mothers with an authoritarian style of upbringing are also avoidance of communication with the child (0.538), especially if the child is dissatisfied with something, intimidation of him with the terrible consequences of his actions (0.614) with the actualization of the state of expectation of punishment, which leads to the development of anxious and suspicious character traits of the child, inability to partner interaction (0.629). In addition, such mothers perceive their family role and the need to be with the child on maternity leave as "martyrdom" (0.584), which is often compensated for by high irritability (0.816) and severity in educational influences (0.575).

The socio-economic characteristics of women adhering to an authoritarian style of upbringing were: the presence of a permanent job, average income, the absence of their own housing, the presence of marital conflicts (0.671). The attitude towards motherhood is associated with the predominance of negative motives for maintaining pregnancy, which is not planned. The following psychological characteristics of mothers with an authoritarian type of upbringing are reliably significant: the emotionally volitional sphere is characterized by a tendency towards inconsistency of goals, difficulties in fulfilling socio-cultural requirements, and high freedom from the influence of group norms (0.644). The emotional sphere is more often saturated, there is expansiveness, a tendency to emotional leadership, impulsivity in interaction (0.679). In addition, the expressed success in establishing and maintaining interpersonal relationships (0.676), entrepreneurial spirit, decisiveness, the ability to not notice difficulties or actively overcome them (0.52).

The group adhering to the democratic style of education consists of 32 people from the total number of participants in the research (25%). According to the data of mathematical analysis, it turned out that women of this group are divided into several types, differing in some parameters that are significant in determining the

specificity of the influence on the child, but there are general patterns that determine the formation of the style of educational influences.

Women with democratic parenting styles are characterized by a high level of harmony in intermarital relations associated with the ability to provide emotional and moral support to each other (0.522). Such couples are characterized by the ability to create a system that allows both partners to develop, while achieving inner comfort and emotional stability of the family. The attitude towards a child in women with a democratic style of upbringing is characterized by optimal emotional contact (0.686), including the ability to build partnerships with a child (0.632), attentiveness to his needs (0.503), stimulating their verbalization (0.587), encouraging children's activity (0.698). The parameter of the desire of such mothers to accelerate the development of the child (0.561) is somewhat ambiguous, which, however, can be explained by the existing fashion for accelerated development.

The psychological characteristics of women in this group include: a high level of sociability, good nature and ease of communication (0.644), the ability to emotional expression; gullibility, which includes tolerance, agreeableness, the ability to care for others and work in a group (0.535); high speed of solving practical problems while focusing on external reality and the ability to maintain a presence of mind in stressful situations (0.503); low anxiety, high level of internal calm (0.529).

The factorial determination of the overprotective (10% of the total sample) style of upbringing is associated with such parameters as: excessive concentration on the child (0.634), expressed in excessive care for him and the creation of the safest possible situation, leading to the formation of dependence relationships. Based on the results of the analysis of the factors, several different components were identified that make up the choice of this strategy: a pronounced phobia of the loss of a child (0.973), his emotional acceptance (0.964), high anxiety (0.927), minimal sanctions against a child (0.869), possibly due to fear of harming him (0.706), suppression of the child's activity (0.924), including the aggressive plan (0.739), the desire to reduce the speed of the child's development (0.881), infantilize him (0.836), while ignoring his needs (0.695). Overcoming the child's resistance and excessive interference in his world can lead to serious psycho-emotional difficulties. The factor of preference for children's qualities in a child (0.565) is a significant factor, which often leads to the development of mental infantilism.

The parental position of such a mother is characterized by the instability of the parenting style (0.960), educational uncertainty (0.719), the limited perception of oneself as a mother (0.869), and the introduction of marital conflicts into education (0.680).

Among the characteristics of the mother, there is a rich imagination (0.934), introversion (0.812), emotional coldness (0.745), fearfulness (0.741), tension (0.627), a tendency to feel guilty (0.656), with high initiative (0.875), discipline (0.601) and ambition (0.791). The child's opinion is not taken into account by

such a mother (0.678), excessive care is observed (0.606) in the absence of adequate requirements for him (0.654). Thus, a reliably expressed psychological property of such a mother is high anxiety, possibly due to personal life circumstances.

Separately, I would like to designate the type of women with a permissive strategy of maternal education, the manifestation of which is combined with high authoritarianism (40% of the sample). The manifestation of this strategy of education is expressed in the following parameters: hypoprotection (0.831); excessive demands on the child (0.733); symbiosis (-0.73); ignoring the needs of the child (0.654); no phobia of loss of a child (0.653); parental obsession, interference with the child's world (-0.652); emotional acceptance of the child (0.597); inability to cooperate (0.590); underdevelopment of parental feelings (0.605); self-confidence, assertiveness (0.557); infantilization of a child (0.541); minimum sanctions (0.516).

Factor analysis made it possible to single out a number of parameters that serve as determinants of the formation of this educational strategy. The psychological characteristics of the mother: independence, sharpness, initiative (0.792); refinement, ambition (0.789); independence, rigidity, practicality (0.608); internal tension, impatience (0.598); willingness to cooperate, sociability (0.578); independence, independence in views (0.540). This is an active type of women, aimed at social interaction and career, with clear leadership inclinations. For such women, motherhood is not a priority and is often regarded as an unpleasant but necessary stage in life.

The socio-economic characteristics of women in this group include a high material status (0.689) and the presence of separate housing (0.593). The main staff are women with higher and secondary specialized education, employed in work, with a good financial situation and good relations with relatives. The leading style of upbringing in the parental family is guardian (0.570), with pronounced characteristics of the second strategy (democratic or authoritarian) and pronounced dominance of the mother (0.533).

The attitude towards motherhood in this group is complicated by the predominance of negative motives for maintaining pregnancy, which is often accidental. For women, the sex of the child is important. The favorite pastimes of these women in childhood are outdoor games or helping adults, loneliness.

Considering the factor content that determines the type of education, it is necessary to group the main parameters into clusters. As a result, the characteristic manifestations were: the presence of the mother's guardian style of upbringing in the parental family, which probably causes a fairly high level of egocentrism, leading to detachment from her own child, with a complex of requirements for independence from the child and from herself. However, at the same time, there is a high willingness to provide the necessary assistance, if the child is able to ask for it. This suggests that this group of mothers may have impaired perception of a small child and there is an expectation of an adult position from him. Negative motives for main-

taining pregnancy, underdevelopment of parental feelings, preference as children's games of activities not related to the formation of maternal behavior, gives us reason to assume a violation of the gestalt of motherhood.

Subsequently, we compared the presence of signs of behavioral disorders in children, dividing mothers into groups according to the leading type of upbringing (Kruskal-Wallis criterion). Significant differences in signs of aggressive behavior of children were observed between the groups of overprotective parenting style and authoritarian ($p \leq 0.05$), permissive ($p \leq 0.05$) parenting styles. According to the parameter of signs of victim behavior in children, a significant difference is observed between the groups of the hyper-protective style of parental attitude (the highest indicator) and the groups of authoritarian ($p \leq 0.05$), democratic ($p \leq 0.05$) styles of upbringing.

Conclusion

An analysis of the regularities of the relationship between the style of upbringing of young children and the strategy of upbringing in the parental family allows us to make an assumption that undoubtedly needs additional research. There is a general tendency to change the style of parenting: the permissive strategy of maternal upbringing, which is characteristic of young women from foster families who are inclined towards a career and expect non-childish behavior from a child, comes to the fore. Emotional coldness and disinterest in psycho-emotional contact with a child can cause corresponding problems in him (various violations of the victim plan, differentiating in accordance with the leading emotional-interpersonal disorders with corresponding behavioral tendencies: a feeling of loneliness, uselessness, abandonment, a tendency to addictions, auto-aggression), leading to mental health problems. The democratic style considered to be adequate is represented in 25% of the sample and is directly related to the parameters of well-being in a married couple and the psychological maturity of the woman herself, which causes serious concern in light of modern trends towards infantilism and the collapse of the family institution. Also, 25% of the subjects demonstrated the authoritarian style of parenting, which is more characteristic of young mothers who have a low level of parental feelings, emotional coldness and a high level of irritation towards the child. Attempts to integrate a small child into their world, without taking into account his needs, leads to his depersonalization and, in the future, the ease of applying various sanctions to him, including cruel treatment. Such a mother's upbringing strategy leads to the emergence of aggressive or passive victim deformations, leading to impaired social functioning and psychological health. Thus, only 25% of children from the studied sample have a chance, within the framework of early education, to receive adequate conditions for the formation of a non-victim type of personality with appropriate interpersonal and personal competencies.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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